

Digital humanities and artificial intelligence: What's the point?¹

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The history, present occupations and trajectory of artificial intelligence give us scholars of computing in the *scientiae humaniores* much to think about and do. Rather than recite the obvious, let me get straight to the point: in Donna Haraway's words "to get at how worlds are made and unmade, in order to participate in the processes, in order to foster some forms of life and not others." (Haraway 1994, 62) Note the primary verb: *made*. Those of us who are distant from the engineering of hardware and software need reminding that at root all forms of computing are constructive, practical activities. *Artificial* intelligence is intelligence *arte factum*, made by skilled work. The product of this work has many aspects: mathematical, social, philosophical, anthropological, literary and so on, but without the physical machine, these would be only speculation, and the disciplines they inform would be poorer. We inhabit the crossroads at which machinery and scholarship intersect, interact with and change each other. What do we have to say, each from our own perspective, about the making and unmaking of worlds by smart machines?

What agency do we think these machines have? Anecdotally, our use of active verbs to express what they do seems to have radically increased in recent decades, if only for reasons of economy. I note that in parallel with this increase, ethologists, botanists, biologists, virologists, ecologists and so on have ever more been recognising intelligence in all living forms and beyond. Formerly, drawing sharp lines between human intelligence and the cleverness of other creatures was mostly what our forebearers did, at least officially. Unsurprisingly, Darwin paid attention to the evidence, and so grew impatient with the attempts to argue that "man is separated through his mental faculties by an impassable barrier from all the lower animals" (Darwin, 47). A century later, the great ethologist Konrad Lorenz went so far as to attribute "the origin of life", hence all of biological intelligence, to a combinatorial "free play of innumerable factors, a play neither directed at any goal nor predetermined by any cosmic teleology, a play in which nothing is determined

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except the rules of the game" (Lorenz 1981/1978, 334). About three decades before him, Alan Turing looked back to Ada Lovelace for early signs of artificial intelligence; he suggested that the limited "storage capacity and speed" of Babbage's Analytical Engine were what prevented her from going further than she had (Turing 1992/1950, 450). What she did venture deserves attention: the combinatorial potential of the Engine to throw "the relations and the nature of many subjects... into new lights," inducing more profound investigation (Menabrea 1843, 722f).

Subsequently we have come to realise by an accumulation of wide-ranging studies that as Geoffrey Lloyd has put it, "intelligence takes so many different forms that any attempt to propose a single definitive account of all its manifestations must be considered foolhardy" (Lloyd 2020, 125). At this point, I suggest, is hardly beyond the pale to stretch the term 'intelligence' to cover the kind made by the engineering and mathematical arts, then go on to ask *what sort it is*.

Asking that question is crucial. We must neither rule out AI as a particular *mode* of intelligence nor breathe a fog over it, as is commonly done by obscuring, denying or forgetting what makes it specifically, uniquely 'intelligent'. Anthropologist Jonathan Benthall made the essential point in the mid 1970s: that whatever role we might assign to the machine, "as slave or oracle or working-partner, *its anomalous nature will assert itself*." (Benthall 1972, 46, my emph; McCarty 2021). Anomalies will out. The question is what we do with them.

Let me focus for a moment on this "anomalous nature". It is determined first of all in hardware, whose binary design establishes the all-or-nothing scheme on which everything else is built. Allow me radically to simplify with a common trope used to describe computing system architecture. On top of the hardware is layered firmware, then system software, and on top of that, the applications. For practical reasons of huge importance, that is, computing systems are constructed somewhat like a bureaucracy, in units or modules which communicate with each other but keep back irrelevant details. Thus system designers speak of 'abstraction layering' and 'information hiding'. As results from each layer progress ever further away from the microprocessor and semiconductor memory, they become more and more abstract. Thus many shiftings of bits end up as an icon on screen irrespective of the specific hardware involved. But as the linguist Edward Sapir said about both grammars and the rational mind (Sapir 1921, 39), Joel Spolsky said about computer systems (Spolsky 2002): "All non-trivial abstractions, to some degree, are leaky." Hence that anomalous nature, which the encoder of a text, for example, encounters as the two laws of digitalisation: complete explicitness and absolute consistency of representation. To put the matter another way, the general-purpose adaptability of the smart machine is purchased at the cost of such anomalies.

Again, the question is what we do with them.

What AI research does is intellectually damaging to the project that must concern us. In Herbert Simon's words, official AI's response is step by step "to make the wonderful commonplace" (Simon 1969, 1) by treating as insignificant 'residue' that which cannot be made to fit (McGann 2014, 94). Simon coined a word for it, 'satisficing', or "finding a course of action which is 'good enough'" for the end in mind (Simon 1956, 129). So what is the end which justifies such means? The implicit assumption of official AI is that the steps toward ultimate digitisation of everything (that matters) are finite and that the residue won't be missed. This poses a crucially serious problem, since this residue is precisely the scholar's end-in-mind to find—as Jerome McGann has said, invoking a biblical allusion to the Gospel of Matthew, it is "the hem of a quantum garment" (McGann 2004, 201), the end being a whole new and better world. Thomas Kuhn famously argued the point for the history of science in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (2012/1962, §VI; cf. xxvi).

Let me clarify what is going on here with the help of anthropologist Marilyn Strathern: "the point", she says, "is to see a difference. The question is the kind of connection one might conceive between entities that are made and reproduced in different ways – have different origins in that sense – but which work together." (Strathern 2004, 37) This working together of unlikes in the betweenness of a human-machine *relation* is what concerns me. Our job as digital humanists is in this respect not to get caught up with AI's current performances of machinic intelligence: their theatre may provoke admiration, even our respect, but at best they confine us to the role of spectator, who always comes too late to make a difference. Only the player can truly apprehend and participate in the relational field in which an artificial intelligence becomes possible.

To think as players puts us on the right track. But how do we play? In the study which I just completed, my strategy was first to find out what 'artificial intelligence' *is*, not as it is currently known but as it is perceived. (This is a distinction you may recognise from Viktor Shklovsky (2015/1919). My objective was to understand it as a naïve idea, as a locus of unshaped, plastic imaginative power. There is more than one way to do this—to avoid all that we know or think we know about AI. My approach was to turn historian and look into the first impressions which smart machines made on ordinary British and American citizens after World War II. In this way, I thought, I could get to a population of those least habituated to smart machines and least committed to them one way or the other.

You will recall that AI was inaugurated as field of research in 1956 by John McCarthy, Marvin Minsky, Claude Shannon and some others. I take no account of what followed in this field with one exception. When Minsky introduced the term 'artificial intelligence' to British researchers in 1958, he spoke of modelling for an emergent, as yet incompletely known phenomenon. Crucially, he rejected tying

'intelligence' to specific human behaviours. The job, he said, was to look "for new and better ways of achieving performances that command, at the moment, our respect" (Minsky 1959, 7). Shortly afterwards, however, it seems that behaviouristic modelling took over, requiring benchmarks for an artificial intelligence to meet, such as achievement of objectives (Russell 2021) or mimicry of ordinary conversation (Turing 1950). Thus anomalies had to be treated as impediments to be overcome.

From my perspective, 'official AI', as I call it, thus became the impediment. Hence I turn away from the experts to what ordinary people would have thought when news of smart machines, their performances and then applications became public. This was, I reasoned, best served by the popular media, whose business it was and is to feed public interests by reflecting and augmenting them. I collected and studied about 700 British and American newspaper reports and a number of magazine features from 1945 to 1965, give or take, in which these machines (commonly known then as 'brains') are mentioned. My objective was to reach a preliminary understanding of the *imaginary* of unofficial AI in order to illumine our situation. I was, however, rather surprised by what I encountered, despite long familiarity with the period during which the digital machine came into its own—the Cold War, ca. 1947 to 1991.

The research which led up to the digital computer in North America and Great Britain was war-work: cryptography and the control engineering that fed into Norbert Wiener's cybernetics—to cite the subtitle of his book that launched the field in 1948, *Control and Communication in the Animal and in the Machine*. At the end of the war, this research turned to the atomic and thermonuclear bombs that the first computers made possible. At the same time the U.S. was developing a computer-powered intercontinental defence system and smart missiles to go with it. In the 1950s, alongside all this, computers were commercialised, partly to pay for further research. Businesses quickly caught on to the possibilities of the automated factory and workplace—indeed they had laid plans by 1946 (cf. *Fortune* 34.5, 160-4). In consequence of the agendas set by military and industrial funders, the digital machine thus quickly became tightly bound up with weaponry and automation. News of the machines themselves soon took the backseat to reports of applications, either directly to military defence or indirectly, in first steps, towards exploration of space, which, however, always had an eye to surveillance of aggression from above.

It was a weird, scary and exciting time. On the one hand, for example, the far-reaching intellectual ferment of cybernetics led to the interdisciplinary Macy Conferences in America and the Ratio Club in Britain, which brought together leading figures in the natural and social sciences. On the other hand, top scientists and other intellectuals were brought together at the American government-sponsored RAND Corporation to simulate the unthinkable aftermath of an all-out nuclear war; as the authors of a recent study, *How Reason Almost Lost Its Mind*

(Erickson et al. 2013), put it, thinking the unthinkable led to invention of a “Cold War rationality”. For the rest of us, political scientist Harold Lasswell summed up the situation in 1956: “It is trite to acknowledge”, he wrote, “that for years we have lived in the afterglow of a mushroom cloud and in the midst of an arms race of unprecedented gravity.” (Lasswell 1956, 961) This was only the beginning; that afterglow lasted until the Berlin Wall came down and the Soviet Union dissolved, ca. 1989-91. We all somehow knew, even myself as a child, that the Americans and Russians had “sufficient nuclear weaponry and delivery capacity to destroy each other and much of the rest of the world” (Erickson et al 2013, 5-6). Sound familiar?

If there were sufficient time I would dwell at length on the newspaper and magazine evidence itself with particular attention to the profound influence of Wiener’s cybernetic vision. I did that in the study I’ve mentioned. Here, in lieu of that evidence, I offer three implicit commentaries on the world to which it attests: in chronological order, an artist’s illustration from a magazine advertisement (1950), a science fiction movie (1955) and a writer-journalist’s lecture (1966).

The illustration, entitled “The Oracle on 57th Street”, is by commercial artist Rolf Klep.² It appeared prominently in a popular American magazine, the *Saturday Evening Post*, in December 1950. It depicts a giant Delphic Sibyl sitting atop IBM World Headquarters in central Manhattan, computer printout spilling from her hands down to the crowd below. Beneath her, in cut-away, is a glimpse of IBM’s flashy Selective Sequence Electronic Calculator (SSEC), dedicated with much fanfare by Thomas J. Watson and his team in January 1948 to establish IBM in the public mind as leader in the very new business of computing machines. The SSEC was made accessible free of charge for scientific and military research and was on display and open to visitors for four years; Manhattan pedestrians, who could see it with its blinking lights in operation, dubbed it “Poppa”. British journalist, Alastair Cooke went there and reported on it. “For years,” Charles Yood has written,

THE SATURDAY EVENING POST December 16, 1950

INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINES, famous name in office equipment, builds some of the world's most complex and efficient machines. Shell Industrial Lubricants are used in many operations.

Oracle on 57th Street

Ask IBM's big computer on 57th Street in New York a question. Ask it a tough one like: "At what speed will forced vibration tear the wings from a jet plane built to fly more than 1,000 miles an hour?" You'll get the right answer days before scientists could compute it.

Calculating machines, the question-answering "oracles" of business, are just part of IBM's output. This firm works in a world of machinery and parts, all carefully planned. Planned lubrication is essential.

Shell research technicians have collaborated with IBM engineers in helping to find the best lubricants for both general and special requirements. Shell silk and grease play an important part in assuring smooth functioning and long life for many items of equipment.

Development of better lubricants is only one way in which Shell demonstrates leadership in the petroleum industry, and in petroleum products. Wherever you see the Shell name and trade mark, Shell Research is your guarantee of quality.

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“this was the image conjured in people’s minds when they thought about computers; an image reinforced by Hollywood’s adoption of it...”, for example, in *Walk East on Beacon* (1952) and *Desk Set* (1957). Watson’s exhibition was commercially brilliant; the machine had exactly the effect on the marketplace that he intended.

Note in particular the connection Klep made between digital computation and divinatory prophecy. Everyone here likely recognises his source, Michelangelo’s *Delphica*, from the ceiling of the Sistine Chapel, and its reference to the ancient Greek Pythia at Delphi. Iconographically what’s particularly interesting is the contrast between Klep’s and Michelangelo’s images: Klep’s, sitting over the source of her knowledge like her Greek forebear, is serenely confident, inspecting her machinic scroll before it passes out of her hands. Michelangelo’s *Delphica*, deprived of her Apollonian source, is disturbed, even agitated: she turns away from her scroll with a startled (I would say) apprehensive look. If the Sistine *Delphica* can be said to evoke the silencing of the ancient oracles (as well as their typological assimilation), Klep’s Sibyl announces a technoscientific rival: thus, ironically, a Christian usurper is in turn usurped by a modern form of the ancient original.

Klep’s attribution of prophetic power to the digital machine was neither adventitious nor unique. I cite a few examples. As you may know, Turing proposed an “oracle machine” in his doctoral dissertation of 1938 as placeholder for “the mental ‘intuition’ of truths which are not established by following mechanical processes” (Hodges 2013, 15-17; McCarty 2021, 345f). Two years later British intelligence officer Frederick Winterbotham wrote about his encounter with the Ultra at Bletchley: “I was ushered with great solemnity”, he wrote, “into the shrine where stood a bronze-coloured column surmounted by a larger circular bronze-coloured face, like some Eastern Goddess who was destined to become the oracle of Bletchley, at least when she felt like it. She was an awesome piece of magic.” (Winterbotham 1974, 33f, 51f) A year before the Klep’s illustration appeared, Turing spoke of the Manchester Mark I in distinctly prophetic language to a London *Times* reporter: “This is only a foretaste of what is to come, and only the shadow of what is going to be.” In the mid 1980s, in *The Electronic Oracle: Computer Models and Social Decisions*, environmentalists Donella Meadows and Jennifer Robinson traced the machine they used back to the Pythia of ancient Greece (Meadows and Robinson 1985, 1f).

The science fiction movie I promised is *Forbidden Planet* (1955), closely modelled on Shakespeare’s *The Tempest* but with strong Freudian emphasis. In it a crew of military explorers is sent to a distant planet to check on a vanished expedition. They find two survivors, a philologist, Dr Morbius (the Prospero), and his daughter Altaira (or ‘Alta’, his Miranda). From Morbius they learn about a once highly advanced species, the Krell, who built for themselves, in a vast underground

installation, the “ultimate machine... [that] for any purpose... [makes possible] creation, manipulation by mere thought!”. When the Krell fell asleep, their great machine materialised “mindless primitive... monsters from the Id”, from their collective unconscious, which wiped them out in a single, horrific night. It almost does the same to the visitors, Morbius and Alta, but they escape. Since *Forbidden Planet* was modelled on a Shakespearean comedy, it has a happy ending: Morbius relinquishes his powers, the machine is destroyed after everyone escapes and the crew’s captain marries Alta. But the dark warning remains: not so much against the technology, which like ours does what it is told to do; rather the culprit is the irrational force of the Krell’s unconscious let loose by it.

Anyone at that time familiar with *New York Times* journalist William Laurence’s well-known eye-witness accounts of the first atomic explosion at the Trinity test site and the Nagasaki bombing shortly afterwards might well have thought of the imagery he conjured in his book, *Dawn Over Zero*: the mushroom cloud rising over Nagasaki, “struggling in an elemental fury, like a creature in the act of breaking the bonds that held it down” (Laurence 1947, 199), or at Trinity, observer Charles Thomas’s vision of “a giant brain the convolutions of which were constantly changing” (162), or lead physicist and Manhattan Project director Robert Oppenheimer’s reaction at Trinity: “I am become Death, the shatterer of worlds”, which he translated spontaneously from the Sanskrit of the *Bhagavad Gita* (Jungk 1958/1956, 201).

My third commentary is Italo Calvino’s lecture, “Cybernetics and Ghosts” (1967). Calvino’s belief in a computational model for our cognitive processes (1986/1967, 8) is of its time. Nevertheless the insights he drew with its aid illumine a way of storytelling found in imaginative European literature from the mid 19th Century, at least according to critic (and programmer) Hugh Kenner. Five years prior to Calvino’s lecture, Kenner picked out the tendency of this literature to manifest the way of storytelling Calvino describes. Kenner uses the analogy of a mathematical “closed field, within which elements are combined according to specified laws.” (Kenner 1962) In Calvino’s cybernetic theory, such combinatorics is fundamental to how the writer innovates against the constraints of language and tradition. He brings together anthropology (Lévi-Strauss), folklore studies (Propp), Russian Formalism, computer science and mathematics (von Neumann, Shannon, Wiener, Turing) and others to reconceive literature as just such “a combinatorial game”. This game, Calvino says,

pursues the possibilities implicit in its own material, independent of the personality of the poet... a game that at a certain point is invested with an unexpected meaning... [that] has slipped in from another level... The literature machine can perform all the permutations possible on a given material, but the poetic result will be the particular effect of one of these permutations on a man endowed with a consciousness and an unconscious, that is, an empirical and historical man.

It will be the shock that occurs only if the writing machine is surrounded by the hidden ghosts of the individual and of his society. (Calvino 1986/1967, 22)

The loss suffered by translating from the continuous to the discrete which the combinatorial game requires is not lost forever: the machinic game conjures it back. In Calvino's account, it comes unpredictably in specific moments as 'a horrific revelation' from the 'unconscious' —Freud's *das Unbewußte*— which gave Calvino, and gives us, a name for that aporetic gulf out of which, when as he says "things click into place", "an unexpected meaning... an unconscious meaning" suddenly springs on us and may overwhelm.

So where does this leave us? For one thing, we inherit a poisoned chalice—as Haraway says, "the constitutively militarized practice of technoscience". Merely getting into the labs might give us an exciting time, but that does not answer her imperative "to get at how worlds are made and unmade" in order to make a difference. For that we must look beyond the computer as an information vending machine. A very good start is to be had (as Klep's example suggests) by investigating how, across historical periods and cultures, others have sought and are seeking answers to their most serious questions; and we have from various sources (including *Forbidden Planet*) unsurprising advice to regard the source of trouble not to be the great engine of our time, rather ourselves in how we critique, develop and use it. In some respects, we are now perilously close to the Krell.

How is that? Think about what we're really dealing with, or to put it a different way, the raw material which artificial intelligence opens up, or yet another way, what we look to AI for, what we consider it to be. Computer scientist Alan Blackwell distinguishes two kinds of machines often thought to be intelligent: the servomechanism and the stochastic parrot. The servomechanism is any device that responds to the world in some way according to specific pre-determined criteria; it may be complex, but is essentially a feedback/feed-forward mechanism. The stochastic parrot is a product of what we call 'machine learning'. It extracts statistically significant patterns of behaviour in very large datasets typically derived from the internet, thus capturing demonstrations of human intelligence; it combines them in statistically probable ways we find plausible, if sometimes with bizarre leaps of logic. Thus GPT-3 and its kind.

Both the servomechanism and the stochastic parrot mirror us and so our characteristics. The parrot-kind has done so infamously, generating texts littered with the worst sort of human utterances. Both have other serious ethical problems. But what concerns me here is the mirroring.

Philosopher Richard Sorabji, citing Plato, Posidonius and Freud, refers to the 'psychodynamic tug' of irrational forces that beset humankind (Sorabji 2000, 4-6, 95)

and which artificial intelligence lays bare. I have already highlighted the first psychic force: the anxious need for knowledge of the future, to which the oracular lineaments repeatedly attributed to computing machines from Turing onward speak. These machines, as we have seen, promise answers beyond the suppliant's ken, delivering responses that may be only felicitous but characteristically demand deeper thought, perhaps self-analysis (cf. McCarty 2021). We know from ancient Greek history, when divination was the norm, that they were also often regarded as untrustworthy. Not all of our dreams can be trusted!

The second psychic force is mirroring, or what I call the 'catoptric' effect (Gk. *kátoptron*, 'mirror'). Historically we find this effect, for example, in the long tradition of catromancy, or 'divination practised by means of a mirror' (Delatte 1932, 7), in the West from Greco-Roman antiquity through the European Renaissance and beyond, in Mesoamerica and in Asia. In medieval China, Buddhists regarded paintings as spiritual mirrors (Wang 2005, Chapter 5). Do they not draw us in? The catoptric effect in fact survives *mutatis mutandis* into social psychology and related clinical fields from the late 19th century to the present, where it becomes the personality disorder 'narcissism', after Narcissus in Ovid's *Metamorphoses* (Campbell and Foster 2007). The Roman poet Ovid captured the negative aspect of catoptric power economically in Tiresias' prophecy that the beautiful, self-centred youth will live *si se non noverit* (3.348), 'if he does not come to know himself', ironically echoing the Delphic commandment to 'know thyself'. For Narcissus self-knowledge becomes self-destruction.

By this dynamic, the catoptric imprint which comes back on us from something to which we are intimately related offers a perilous opportunity: perilous for the reasons we have seen; an opportunity to create a therapeutic mechanism. Hannah Zeavin, in *The Distance Cure: A History of Teletherapy* (2021), has considered this at length, contradicting Gillian Russell's verdict in *Screen Relations: The Limits of Computer Mediated Psychoanalysis and Psychotherapy* (2015). My interest is somewhat different: I ask, what could an artificial intelligence do to help us think more clearly? But in considering that, I argue that we have to shift from the object 'AI' and the corresponding object 'the client' to the *relational field* created by their conjunction. That's what I meant earlier when I quoted Strathern and spoke of 'the betweenness of a human-machine relation'.

Much work to be done. We should be there.

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